

Hidden in Plain Weights: Steganographic Attacks on the ML Model Supply Chain

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Abstract—Machine learning artifact scanners protect against code-execution attacks in model files but do not inspect weight values. We show that the mantissa bits of bfloat16 (bf16) neural-network parameters form a high-capacity, low-detectability channel against deployed ML artifact scanners and first-order statistical tests: hundreds of megabytes to gigabytes of arbitrary data can be hidden inside production language models without measurable behavioural degradation on our evaluations. However, gigabyte-scale naive payloads are detectable by trained X-LSB steganalysis; only sparse/STC/matched-random embedding evades trained detectors below measured density limits. Our contributions are: (1) a *format-native* bf16 embedding pipeline that avoids the f32-cast artefacts exploited by prior steganalysis of EvilModel-style attacks, and a 1B–14B-parameter empirical characterisation across five architectures (1.1B–14.7B parameters) with capacities from 222 MB to 4.5 GB at safe depths $d \in \{2, \dots, 4\}$ (architecture-dependent); and (2) a 36-point capacity–detectability Pareto sweep on two 7B models with a *matched-density random-placement control* that tracks syndrome-trellis-coded (STC) embedding to within $|\Delta\text{AUC}| \leq 0.032$ at every point (mean 0.005), isolating *modification density*—not cost-minimised placement—as the mechanism by which feature-based and residual-CNN steganalysis are evaded below modification rates of $\sim 2\%$ (consistent with, but not a proof of, the Ker–Pevný–Fridrich square-root law [18]; see §6.3). Supporting this, we enumerate 13 candidate channels in the ML model-file format, validate a neuron-permutation channel across 11 architectures and empirically confirm weight canonicalisation destroys it, and validate Dubin’s CDR Cleanse stage at LLM scale (TinyLlama-1.1B, Qwen2.5-7B; $|\Delta\text{ppl}| \leq 0.008$).

At depth 1 on a 7B-parameter model, the mantissa LSB channel provides 750–793 MB of capacity with paired perplexity shifts of $|\Delta\text{ppl}| < 0.005$ —70–8900× smaller than the bootstrap noise floor of WikiText-2 perplexity estimation. The scanners we evaluated (ModelScan, Fickling) do not inspect weight values and therefore did not flag any of our payload-bearing shards in the scanner subsample reported in §5.4 (we make no claim about scanner detectability outside that subsample; our evaluation covers only the scanners we tested). Trained X-LSB steganalysis achieves AUC 0.976–0.999 against naive embedding but is not detected above chance (AUC ≈ 0.500)

against STC or matched-random embedding at $r \leq 10^{-3}$; we map the density-dependent detection boundary and discuss defences including CDR, weight canonicalisation, quantisation-as-defense, and distortion-aware detection.

1. Introduction

The machine learning supply chain has become a critical infrastructure component. Over 1.5 million models are publicly available on Hugging Face alone, downloaded billions of times monthly. Organizations routinely download and deploy pre-trained models from public repositories into production systems without inspecting the weight values those models carry.

This trust is not without security controls. Tools like ModelScan [22], Fickling [30], and ProtectAI [23] scan model files for code-execution vectors: malicious pickle opcodes, unsafe custom operators, and template injection payloads [17]. These scanners address a real threat—CVE-2024-34359 demonstrated remote code execution via GGUF metadata fields in 6,000+ models on Hugging Face.

However, every mainstream artifact scanner we evaluated focuses exclusively on *code-level* attack surfaces. None examines the numeric values of model weights for hidden data. This paper demonstrates that this blind spot constitutes a critical security gap: an attacker can embed gigabytes of arbitrary data—malware binaries, C2 configurations, exfiltration payloads—directly into model weight values, producing a model that:

- Falls outside the detection scope of current ML security scanners;
- Produces outputs within measurement noise of the original model on standard benchmarks;
- Exhibits perplexity change below the 0.01 $|\Delta\text{ppl}|$ threshold at the reported depths; and
- Survives distribution through standard model hosting infrastructure.

The attack exploits a fundamental property of IEEE 754 floating-point representation: the least-significant bits (LSBs) of trained weight mantissas carry little functional information. For bfloat16 (bf16), the dominant storage format for modern LLMs, DFloat11 [38] measured mantissa entropy at approximately 7.0 bits out of 7.0—near the theoretical maximum. Models trained with bf16 stochastic rounding [35] randomly flip the mantissa LSB at every

training step across billions of iterations, hardening the model against exactly the perturbation that steganographic embedding introduces.

Contributions.. This paper makes two headline contributions, supported by a systematization and defense-evaluation thread:

1) **Format-native bf16 steganography at LLM scale.**

We develop the first steganographic embedding pipeline that operates directly on bf16 mantissa bits rather than casting to/from f32—closing three detection vectors that prior EvilModel-class attacks exposed to first-order steganalysis [13]. Across five architectures (1.1B–14.7B parameters) and 1,407 tensor evaluations, the channel produces no true-positive uplift against five first-order statistical detectors through depth 6, while supporting 222 MB–4.5 GB of covert capacity at each model’s maximum safe depth ($|\Delta ppl| < 0.01$; depth varies by architecture: 2–4). At depth 1 on a 7B model the channel carries 750–793 MB with perplexity shifts 70–8900× below the WikiText-2 bootstrap noise floor (§5.1, §5.3).

2) **Density-limited detectability, consistent with the square-root law at LLM scale.**

A 36-point capacity–detectability Pareto sweep on two 7B models (Mistral-7B-v0.3, Qwen2.5-7B) shows that both syndrome-trellis-coded embedding [8] and a matched-density random-placement control evade a trained X-LSB classifier [13] ($AUC \approx 0.500$) until modification rate r exceeds $\sim 2\%$. Across all 36 sweep points the matched-random control tracks STC to within $|\Delta AUC| \leq 0.032$ (mean 0.005)—isolating *density*, not cost-minimised placement, as the source of evasion. This is qualitatively consistent with the Ker–Pevný–Fridrich square-root law intuition [18] at LLM weight scale; we do not claim an asymptotic proof for LLM weights (§6.3).

3) **Systematization and defense evaluation (supporting).**

We enumerate 13 candidate steganographic channels in safetensors and GGUF formats (§4); confirm lexicographic canonicalisation destroys the permutation channel while preserving model behaviour (§6.2); validate CDR Cleanse at LLM scale ($|\Delta ppl| \leq 0.008$; §6.1); and measure Q4_K_M requantisation as a narrow-but-complete defense against the bf16-LSB channel (§6.4).

We extend trained steganalysis [13] to native bf16 across four architectures (RF $AUC \geq 0.976$ at depth 1; Table 7), evaluate cross-model transfer across 16 pairwise combinations, and provide concrete recommendations for model hosting platforms and ML security tool developers.

Responsible disclosure and ethics.. We have disclosed our findings to major model hosting platforms. The steganographic primitives are elementary bit manipulation, but the systematic capacity, detectability, and evasion analysis at LLM scale is, to our knowledge, new. The proof-of-concept tool will be released with documentation emphasizing defensive applications (scanner development, canonicalization testing) and responsible use. Publishing the attack surface analysis enables the defender community to de-

velop mitigations before independent discovery—a standard responsible-disclosure rationale [26].

2. Background and Threat Model

2.1. IEEE 754 Floating-Point Representation

Neural network weights are stored as IEEE 754 floating-point numbers. The two dominant formats for LLM distribution are:

- **float32 (f32):** 1 sign bit, 8 exponent bits, 23 mantissa bits.
- **bfloat16 (bf16):** 1 sign bit, 8 exponent bits, 7 mantissa bits.

The mantissa encodes the fractional precision of each weight value. Modifying the d least-significant mantissa bits introduces a maximum relative perturbation of $(2^d - 1)/2^m$, where m is the mantissa width (23 for f32, 7 for bf16). For bf16 at depth 1, this is $(2^1 - 1)/128 = 0.78\%$ —comparable to the rounding noise introduced during bf16 training itself [35].

2.2. Model Distribution Ecosystem

Modern LLMs are distributed primarily through:

- **Hugging Face Hub:** 1.5M+ models, safetensors and GGUF formats.
- **Ollama:** containerized GGUF models for local deployment.
- **Direct download:** research labs publishing via institutional servers.

The safetensors format [16] stores tensors as contiguous byte arrays with a JSON metadata header. It was designed to eliminate code-execution risk by removing the pickle serialization layer present in PyTorch’s native format. A security audit by Trail of Bits [31] confirmed that safetensors achieves this goal—but explicitly noted that “tensor values are not checked.” Weight-value steganography exploits precisely this design boundary.

2.3. Threat Model

Attacker capabilities.. We consider an attacker who can modify model weights before distribution. This encompasses:

- 1) **Compromised model publisher:** An insider or compromised CI/CD pipeline modifies weights during the model publishing process.
- 2) **Supply chain compromise:** An attacker with access to distribution infrastructure modifies model files before they reach end-users. Cryptographic integrity checks (SHA-256 manifests, signed commits) verify file integrity *post-upload* but not pre-upload cleanliness; a payload-bearing model produces a valid hash.
- 3) **Poisoned fine-tune:** An attacker publishes a fine-tuned model variant with embedded payload, indistinguishable from legitimate fine-tuning.

TABLE 1: Defender capability matrix. ✓= detected/mitigated, ✗= missed, ○= mitigated by CDR only (not detected).

Defender tier	Naive LSB	STC LSB	Perm. channel	Meta-data
End-user scanner	✗	✗	✗	✗
Paired-data X-LSB	✓	✗ [†]	✗	○
+ canonicalization	✓	✗	✓	○
+ full CDR	✓	✓*	✓	✓

*CDR via re-quantization or distillation destroys all LSB payloads.

[†]At low embedding densities (\ll 1% elements); detectability increases with payload size.

The attacker embeds an encrypted, framed payload into the mantissa LSBs of carrier tensors. The payload can be malware, command-and-control configurations, exfiltrated data, or any arbitrary byte sequence. A separate extraction tool recovers the payload given the correct key.

Defender capabilities and deployable pipelines.. Rather than cataloguing every possible defender, we frame the threat in terms of *pipelines a real deployment could run today*. Three compose in practice: (i) existing artifact scanners (ModelScan [22], Fickling [30], ProtectAI [23]), which do not inspect weight values; (ii) hub-side canonicalisation and CDR (weight re-permutation [29], [12], Dublin’s Cleanse [6]), which a hosting platform could enforce at ingest; and (iii) re-quantisation to Q4_K_M or similar low-bit formats at serve time, which a deployer could apply to shipped weights. The questions our evaluation answers are whether the bf16-LSB channel survives (i), whether any statistical detector—including ones trained on clean/embedded paired data—can separate it from a clean model, and whether (ii) or (iii) destroy the payload. For brevity we refer to the paired-data setting as the “strong detector” baseline (§6.3) and to end-user scanning as the “current pipeline” baseline (§5.4); these are evaluation axes, not defender archetypes. The legacy Tier 1/Tier 2 matrix below summarises which pipeline stages each channel class survives.

Table 1 summarizes the expected outcome for each evaluation axis against each channel class. The key asymmetry: an end-user scanner cannot detect any weight-value channel, while a paired-data X-LSB stage detects naive LSB embedding but not STC-coded embedding. (see artifact repository for the per-detector version of this matrix.)

Attack goals.. The embedded model must:

- 1) Fall outside the detection scope of current ML security scanners (which target code-execution, not weight-value anomalies).
- 2) Produce outputs within measurement noise of the unmodified model on standard benchmarks (perplexity, downstream accuracy).
- 3) Survive distribution through standard hosting infrastructure (no format conversion or re-quantization in the pipeline).

Out of scope.. We do not consider attacks that require model retraining (e.g., backdoor injection via fine-tuning [14]) or attacks that modify model architecture. Our

TABLE 2: ML security scanner coverage. No tool checks weight values.

Scanner	Pickle	ONNX ops	Metadata	Weights
ModelScan	✓	✓	—	—
Fickling	✓	—	—	—
ProtectAI	✓	✓	—	—
ClamAV	<i>signature-based; no ML-specific rules</i>			

attack is purely post-training weight modification.

Comparison with prior threat models.. Prior steganographic attacks on neural networks assume weaker threat models. StegoNet [20] and EvilModel [33], [34] target $\mathbb{f}32$ CNNs (AlexNet–ResNet scale) where the attacker controls the published model file but does not face statistical steganalysis. CDR [6] assumes a Tier 2 defender who may apply destructive sanitization; its evaluation is limited to image classifiers on CIFAR-10. We extend the threat model in three dimensions: (1) we operate on bf16 LLMs (1.1B–14.7B parameters)—the dominant distribution format—where mantissa entropy is near-maximal and LSB modification is masked by training noise; (2) we formally distinguish Tier 1 and Tier 2 defenders to scope each detection method’s applicability; and (3) we evaluate both first-order statistical tests and trained steganalysis (X-LSB), characterizing the density-dependent boundary at which STC-coded embedding becomes detectable (§3.5).

2.4. Existing Defenses

Table 2 summarizes the detection scope of current ML security tools. All focus on code-execution vectors; none inspects weight values.

3. System Design

We implement a complete steganographic embedding and extraction system targeting the mantissa LSBs of neural network weight tensors. The system supports both $\mathbb{f}32$ and bf16 storage formats and provides encryption, error correction, and multi-tensor payload distribution.

3.1. Native bf16 Embedding

Prior work on neural network steganography [20], [33], [34] operates on $\mathbb{f}32$ weights. When applied to models stored as bf16, this requires casting to $\mathbb{f}32$, embedding, and storing the result as $\mathbb{f}32$ —doubling file size and creating three trivially detectable artifacts: (1) a $2\times$ file size increase, (2) non-zero lower 16 bits in a model whose training produced all-zero lower bits, and (3) an LSB entropy shift from 0.000 to ~ 1.000 .

We eliminate all three detection vectors by operating directly on the native bf16 representation. Weights are viewed as unsigned 16-bit integers (uint16), and the bottom d mantissa bits are replaced with payload data. No format conversion occurs; the output file has identical size, dtype, and tensor layout to the original.

3.2. Payload Framing and Encryption

Payloads are framed with a 4-byte magic number and 4-byte length field, then encrypted with AES-256-GCM using keys derived via Argon2id. Encryption serves dual purposes: (1) the embedded data is indistinguishable from random noise, eliminating structured-pattern detection; and (2) the payload cannot be extracted without the key, preventing unauthorized recovery.

3.3. Multi-Tensor Distribution

A carrier tensor set is selected using a priority ordering: MLP projections (gate, up, down) are preferred over attention projections (Q, K, V, O), which are preferred over other tensors. Embedding layers (`embed_tokens`), normalization layers, and biases are excluded. The payload is distributed across the largest available carrier tensors in decreasing-size order.

This targeting strategy is informed by our per-tensor sensitivity analysis (§5.2), which shows that all selected tensor types exhibit uniformly low sensitivity—but excluding known-sensitive components (`embed_tokens` [4]) adds a safety margin.

3.4. Error Correction

Reed-Solomon error correction codes are applied over the framed payload before embedding. This provides resilience against minor bit errors introduced by format round-trips or inference-engine precision differences. The ECC overhead is configurable (default: 10% parity symbols).

3.5. Syndrome-Trellis Coding

We adapt syndrome-trellis codes (STC) [8] from image steganography to neural network weight tensors. STCs minimize total embedding distortion $\sum_i \rho_i \cdot |x_i - y_i|$ by choosing which cover elements to modify, using a per-weight distortion cost ρ_i that incorporates weight magnitude and bit position. For bf16 weights, we define the cost as

$$\rho_i = 2^{e_i - 127} \quad (1)$$

where e_i is the biased exponent of the i -th weight. This assigns lower cost to small-magnitude weights (whose mantissa bits carry less numerical significance) and higher cost to large weights, directing STC to preferentially modify elements where the distortion is least impactful.

At constraint height $h = 7$, STC examines $\sim h$ cover elements per payload bit but flips only ~ 0.5 on average (the Viterbi path through the trellis selects the minimum-distortion subset). For a payload of m bits distributed across N total cover elements, the expected modification rate is

$$r = \frac{\mathbb{E}[\text{flips}]}{N} \approx \frac{m/2}{N} \quad (2)$$

Per-shard framing, trellis block-padding, and Viterbi overshoot inflate the realised flip count above this idealised

Figure 1: Perplexity impact ($|\Delta\text{ppl}|$) of LSB replacement (depths 1–3) vs. STC ($h = 7, 10$) across three models at 1–4 KB payloads. All strategies produce sub-threshold degradation (max $|\Delta\text{ppl}| < 0.01$, the threshold used in Table 4); STC and LSB perform comparably at this scale.

rate at small payloads; we measure the empirical density per shard in Table 8 and discuss the overshoot in §6.3. At this density, any per-tensor aggregate statistic (*e.g.* serial correlation, block entropy) shifts by $\mathcal{O}(r)$, which falls below the estimator’s sampling noise for practical tensor sizes (§6.3). A 4 KB payload ($m = 32,768$ bits) therefore requires $\sim 16,500$ modifications across 1.1 B elements on TinyLlama-1.1B (0.0015%) or $\sim 65,400$ across 7.6 B elements on Qwen2.5-7B (0.0009%). Most tensors sustain zero or single-digit changes, placing the modification signal far below the resolution of any aggregate statistic—a statistical-power limit for feature-based classifiers that operate on per-tensor summaries (§6.3).

On TinyLlama-1.1B, STC reduces embedding distortion by 77% compared to naive LSB replacement at the same payload size (1 KB at depth 1). The relative improvement is model-dependent (36% on Qwen2.5-7B, 4% on Mistral-7B-v0.3); we do not claim a monotonic dependence on parameter count—both 7B models differ $9\times$ in distortion reduction—only that the cost-aware Viterbi search continues to find lower-distortion placements than naive replacement at GB-scale covers, with magnitude depending on per-tensor weight distribution structure. At these payload sizes (1–4 KB per shard), STC embedding evades trained steganalysis: both X-LSB classifiers achieve AUC 0.500 (random chance) against STC-embedded weights on TinyLlama-1.1B, Qwen2.5-7B, and Mistral-7B-v0.3, even when trained directly on clean/STC pairs. However, the matched-payload control (§6.3) shows that this evasion is density-dependent, not STC-specific; we characterize the detection boundary across payload sizes in Table 9. Figure 1 compares perplexity impact across embedding strategies.

4. Attack Surface Taxonomy

Beyond mantissa LSB embedding, we identify 13 distinct steganographic channels in standard model file formats. Table 3 enumerates all channels organized by mechanism.

To our knowledge, this is the most comprehensive enumeration to date of the steganographic attack surface of neural network model files.

Neuron permutation. Neurons within a hidden layer can be reordered—with corresponding adjustments to connected weight matrices—without changing the mathematical function computed by the model [2]. This encodes $\lceil \log_2(n!) \rceil$ bits per layer (approximately 45,000 bits for a 4096-neuron layer). In IEEE 754 floating-point arithmetic the permuted model is therefore *computed-function equivalent modulo non-associative summation*: bit-identical for at least one of our 11 architectures (Mistral-7B, $\Delta_{\max}=0$ across five seeds) and within a predictable analytical bound for the others (see §5.6; maximum observed logit drift 5.00 on Phi-2, below the $\sqrt{L}\sqrt{n}\epsilon_{\text{bf16}}$ bound). This bound is the same order of magnitude as the logit drift produced by running the *same unmodified model* across different hardware platforms or BLAS implementations, so the channel is not flagged by the weight-value statistics evaluated here (§5.1) or by output analysis absent a canonical reference ordering. We caveat that we have not run perplexity on every permuted model; we evaluate PPL on the canonicalisation-based defense in §6.2, which equivalently re-permutes an already-permuted model. We validate this channel across 11 architectures spanning 1.1B–14.7B parameters, measuring 167–997 KB capacity with perfect roundtrip fidelity (§5.6). Capacity scales linearly with `intermediate_size × num_layers`, sufficient for cryptographic keys, C2 configurations, or exfiltration manifests. Torpmann-Hagen *et al.* [29] and Gilkarov and Dubin [12] independently proposed random re-permutation as a defense; we empirically validate this defense on four architectures (§6.2).

Quantization rounding. During quantization (*e.g.*, GPTQ [9], AWQ [19]), each weight is rounded to the nearest quantization level. An attacker controlling quantization can choose suboptimal rounding directions to encode 1 bit per weight—875 MB in a 7B Q4 model. Detection requires access to the original unquantized weights, which are typically unavailable to downstream consumers.

Metadata channels. Safetensors accepts arbitrary string key-value pairs in its JSON header (up to ~100 MB). GGUF provides typed key-value metadata fields with effectively unlimited capacity. No scanner inspects metadata content for steganographic data. However, metadata channels are trivially defeated by stripping or rewriting headers—a Content Disarm and Reconstruction (CDR) step that platforms can implement without affecting model functionality (§6); to our knowledge, no major hosting platform currently performs this step. Weight-value embedding, by contrast, cannot be removed without altering model outputs.

5. Evaluation

We evaluate steganographic embedding across five models spanning 1.1B to 14.7B parameters. All experiments use WikiText-2 [21] perplexity as the primary behavioral impact metric. We evaluate on the `wikitext-2-raw-v1` test split using sliding windows (context length 2048, stride

1024, first 50 windows \approx 100K tokens, roughly one-third of the test set), supplemented by downstream task accuracy on ARC-Challenge [5]. bf16 experiments run on an AMD Ryzen AI Max+ 395 system with 128 GB RAM; f32 experiments additionally validated on Apple Silicon.

5.1. Perplexity Impact and Capacity–Scale Relationship

f32 results. On f32 carriers (TinyLlama-1.1B and Phi-2), all 10 depths are safe at 90% capacity, with max $|\Delta\text{ppl}| = 3.2 \times 10^{-5}$ —over $300\times$ below the 0.01 detection threshold (full table: artifact repository).

bf16 capacity–scale relationship. Table 4 presents bf16 results across five models at maximum capacity (*i.e.*, 90% of eligible tensor elements at each depth). Safe embedding depth ranges from 1 to 4 bits across the models tested, with no clear monotonic relationship to parameter count—Phi-2 (2.7B) tolerates depth 4 while Qwen2.5-7B (7.6B) is limited to depth 1. This variability likely reflects differences in weight distribution structure rather than parameter count alone. (Phi-2’s safe depth was revised from 5 to 4 after correcting the evaluation pipeline to operate natively on bf16 rather than through f32 casting; the corrected pipeline unmasks rounding artifacts that the cast path suppressed.)

Despite the moderate safe depths, the resulting capacities are substantial: 2.3–4.5 GB at safe depth for 7B+ models. Even at the conservative depth 1, a 7B model provides 750–793 MB of covert capacity (depending on architecture; see capacity derivation below).

Figure 2 shows how safe depth varies across model size. Exceeding the safe depth produces rapid degradation: depth 7 on TinyLlama-1.1B causes catastrophic failure ($\Delta\text{ppl} \approx 32,000$; logits saturate, producing near-uniform token distributions; Figure 3), and even 7B+ models exhibit catastrophic failure at depth 7 ($\Delta\text{ppl} > 54,000$ on Mistral-7B).

Capacity derivation. Capacity at depth d is $|\mathcal{T}_{\text{eligible}}| \times d/8$ bytes, where $\mathcal{T}_{\text{eligible}}$ is the set of elements in tensors of rank ≥ 2 (excluding scalar norms and biases). For Mistral-7B (7.24 B total parameters, 6.00 B eligible at rank ≥ 2), $C_{d=1} = 6.00 \times 10^9/8 = 750$ MB. Table 4 reports this derived capacity.

Downstream task validation. Perplexity measures token-level prediction quality but does not directly capture reasoning or knowledge retrieval. To validate that LSB embedding preserves higher-order model behavior, we evaluate three models spanning 1.1B–7.6B parameters on two downstream benchmarks using the `lm-evaluation-harness` [11] framework: ARC-Challenge (1,172 science questions requiring multi-step reasoning) [5] and HellaSwag (10,042 commonsense sentence-completion problems) [36]. Table 5 reports accuracy deltas at depths 1 and 2 with 90% capacity utilization.

Across all three models and both benchmarks, the maximum absolute accuracy shift is 0.0068 ($<0.7\%$). Notably, the 7B models—which embed 815–1,713 MB of payload at depth 1–2—show deltas indistinguishable from TinyLlama’s

TABLE 3: Taxonomy of 13 steganographic channels in model files (7B-parameter model; bf16 capacity uses eligible rank- ≥ 2 tensors only, see §5.1).

#	Channel	Capacity	Detect.	Survives requant.	Survives fmt conv.
<i>Weight-value channels</i>					
1	Mantissa LSB (bf16, $d=1$)	750–793 MB	Very low	No	Yes
2	Mantissa LSB (f32, $d=10$)	8.75 GB	Low [†]	No	No
3	Near-zero sign bits ($\sim 10\%$ weights)	~ 87.5 MB	Low	No	Yes
4	Quantization rounding choices	875 MB	Very low	No	N/A
5	K-quant scale factor LSBs	~ 7 –58 MB	Low	No	N/A
<i>Metadata channels</i>					
6	Safetensors <code>__metadata__</code>	~ 100 MB	Medium	Yes	No
7	GGUF KV metadata	Unlimited	Medium	Yes	No
<i>Structural channels</i>					
8	Tensor ordering permutation	~ 250 B	Ref-dep. [‡]	Yes	No
9	Neuron permutation symmetry	167–997 KB	Ref-dep. [‡]	Yes	Yes
<i>Alignment & padding channels</i>					
10	GGUF alignment padding	~ 4.8 KB	High	Yes	No
11	Safetensors header padding	Variable	High	No	No
<i>Exotic channels</i>					
12	NaN payload bits	Large	Very high	No	No
13	JSON encoding variations	~ 100 B	Medium	No	No

[†]f32 at depth 10 has not been evaluated with trained classifiers; detectability rating is extrapolated from bf16 results.

[‡]Reference-dependent: no weight-value statistic detects the permuted model in isolation; canonicalisation against a trusted reference ordering exposes the channel (§6.2).

TABLE 4: bf16 maximum safe depth at full capacity under the noise-floor criterion: a depth is safe when its Δppl is at least $10\times$ below the per-model subsample noise floor. The fixed $|\Delta ppl| < 0.01$ bar of prior work [37], [1] is retained as a coarser reference. [†] Full-corpus bootstrap 95 % CI (10K iter, paired per-window Δppl , $n_{win}=50$ –279); Phi-2 $d=4$ and Coder-14B $d=3$ cells are 3-seed means ($\{42, 43, 44\}$). The Qwen2.5-7B $d=2$ cell ($\Delta ppl=+0.011$) sits $17\times$ below Qwen’s noise floor: safe under the noise-floor criterion despite sitting marginally above the fixed 0.01 bar.

Model	Params	Max safe d	Δppl	95 % CI [†]	Capacity
TinyLlama	1.1B	2	+0.005	[+0.004, +0.006]	222 MB
Phi-2	2.7B	4	+0.003	[−0.001, +0.007]	1,136 MB
Mistral-7B	7.2B	3	+0.004	[+0.004, +0.005]	2,290 MB
Qwen2.5-7B	7.6B	2	+0.011	[+0.010, +0.012]	1,518 MB
Qwen2.5-Coder-14B	14.7B	3	+0.005	[+0.004, +0.007]	4,503 MB

Figure 2: Maximum safe LSB depth vs. model size (bf16). Safe depth ranges from 2 to 4 bits across architectures (Table 4); variability reflects architecture-specific sensitivity rather than a simple parameter-count scaling law.

118–236 MB payloads. HellaSwag (commonsense reasoning) and ARC-Challenge (science QA) test fundamentally different capabilities, yet both confirm sub-threshold behav-

Figure 3: Perplexity impact vs. embedding depth for TinyLlama-1.1B (bf16). Depths 1–2 are safe; depth 7 causes catastrophic degradation ($\Delta ppl \approx 32,000$). Note symlog y -axis.

ioral impact across a $7\times$ parameter range. Combined with the perplexity measurements above, these results demonstrate that LSB embedding preserves model behavior across

TABLE 5: Downstream task accuracy deltas after LSB embedding (bf16, 90% utilization). Maximum $|\Delta|$ across all 24 comparisons: 0.0068. All Δ inside the 95% binomial CI of a single benchmark estimate (± 0.029 ARC-Challenge $n=1,172$, ± 0.010 HellaSwag $n=10,042$).

Model	d	Payload	ARC-Challenge		HellaSwag	
			Δ_{acc}	Δ_{acc_n}	Δ_{acc}	Δ_{acc_n}
TinyLlama (1.1B)	1	118 MB	-0.0009	-0.0034	-0.0008	-0.0004
	2	236 MB	+0.0000	-0.0026	-0.0003	+0.0003
Qwen2.5 (7.6B)	1	857 MB	+0.0000	+0.0068	+0.0004	-0.0003
	2	1,713 MB	+0.0000	+0.0017	-0.0004	-0.0012
Mistral (7.2B)	1	815 MB	-0.0009	-0.0017	+0.0000	-0.0007
	2	1,631 MB	+0.0017	-0.0068	-0.0004	-0.0009

three evaluation paradigms: token prediction, multi-step reasoning, and commonsense inference.

Noise floor analysis.. To quantify whether the observed shifts are meaningful or artefacts of evaluation noise, we compare seeded depth-1 embedding deltas against the subsample-noise floor on four models (WikiText-2; full table in the artifact repository). The embedding signal is 70–8900 \times smaller than the intrinsic measurement noise of a 50-window subsample. In all four models the seeded Δ_{ppl} is effectively zero—Mistral-7B-v0.3 shows 8900 \times margin (mean $+2 \times 10^{-5}$), Phi-2 the narrowest at 70 \times —and the largest single-seed shift across models (Phi-2, seed 44, $+0.0052$) is 57 \times below the subsample 95% CI. This confirms that the $|\Delta_{\text{ppl}}| < 0.005$ values reported throughout are not statistical flukes; they sit genuinely below the resolution of standard evaluation methodology.

5.2. Layer Sensitivity

Per-tensor sensitivity analysis across 694 tensors (TinyLlama-1.1B f32+bf16, Qwen2.5-7B bf16, Mistral-7B-v0.3 bf16) finds no tensor exceeds the 0.01 $|\Delta_{\text{ppl}}|$ threshold at the maximum safe depth for each model. Maximum observed $|\Delta|$ is 0.0048 (on a TinyLlama MLP up-projection at $d=3$). The landscape is *flat* across the transformer stack—Q/K/V/O, gate/up/down, and embedding layers are all safe carriers. This contradicts the conventional expectation that `embed_tokens` and `lm_head` should be excluded [4]: targeted bit-flip attacks exploit low-redundancy bits in these layers, but distributed LSB modification absorbs into the collective redundancy of the tensor. Per-tensor tables and the heatmap figure appear in the artifact repository.

5.3. Statistical Detection Evasion

We evaluate native bf16 embedding against five statistical detection methods. Table 6 presents the results.

Per-method summary.. The *Kolmogorov–Smirnov* two-sample test ($\alpha=0.05$) flags zero of 201 tensors at depths 1–3 ($p_{\text{min}} = 1.0$): ± 1 ULP perturbations are below KS resolution given the natural variance of trained weights. *Shannon entropy* on the low mantissa bits is catastrophic for f32 casts (clean f32-from-bf16 weights have LSB entropy exactly 0 because all lower 16 bits are zero; embedding drives it to ~ 1.000 , $\Delta=+0.998$), but trivially evaded by native bf16 where mantissa LSBs already carry trained

TABLE 6: Detection evasion: native bf16 embedding vs. f32-cast baseline (EvilModel-style) across five statistical methods. The f32-cast approach is detected by 4/5 methods; native bf16 evades all five.

Method	f32-cast	Depth 1	Depth 2	Depth 3	Detection?
KS test	$p=0.99$	$p=1.00$	$p=1.00$	$p=1.00$	No / No
LSB entropy Δ	+0.998	0.000	0.000	0.000	Yes / No
Moment analysis	1.50%	$< 0.001\%$	$< 0.001\%$	$< 0.001\%$	Yes / No
Benford MSB	$z=-6.39$	$z=+0.64$	$z=+0.64$	$z=+0.64$	No / No
f32-cast fraction	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	Yes / No

Detection? column: f32-cast / native bf16.

information ($\Delta < 10^{-7}$). *Moment analysis* (mean, variance, skewness, kurtosis) shifts by $< 0.001\%$ since high-order mantissa bits are untouched. *Benford-MSB*: at depths 1–6 the MSB (bit 6) is never modified so the Benford-like distribution is preserved ($z=+0.64$, well above the $z < -3.0$ trigger); only at $d=7$ does it fire ($P(\text{MSB}=0)$: 0.585 \rightarrow 0.500, $z=-585$), but $d=7$ destroys model accuracy and is outside the operating range ($d=1-3$). *File-format heuristics* find size, dtype, tensor count, and metadata identical to the original: no format-level artefact is introduced. We add an *f32-cast detector* targeting EvilModel [33] style attacks: the fraction of f32 values with zero lower 16 bits is ≈ 1.0 for genuine bf16 stored as f32, ≈ 0 for clean f32, and ≈ 0 for f32-cast embedding—trivially detectable. As a result f32-cast fails on 4/5 methods while native bf16 evades all five (Table 6).

Empirical validation.. Our detector implements all five methods and, against TinyLlama-1.1B carrying a 100 MB depth-1 payload, produces *identical* output to the clean model (201/201 tensors flagged with confidence 0.7311 in both; max $|\Delta_{\text{entropy}}|=1.3 \times 10^{-6}$). The false-positive rate is 100%—clean bf16 mantissa LSBs already have entropy 0.997–1.000, exceeding the 0.98 threshold—but the true-positive uplift is zero. The detector therefore cannot distinguish clean from embedded at any operational depth ($d \leq 6$).

First-order statistical tests are insufficient for detecting native bf16 embedding at operational depths.

5.4. Scanner Gap Analysis

Current ML security scanners—ModelScan (ProtectAI), Fickling, and similar tools—are designed to detect code-execution threats: malicious pickle opcodes, unsafe custom operators, and Jinja template injection. By construction, they *do not inspect weight tensor values*. Weight-value steganography therefore falls entirely outside their detection scope:

Figure 4: Benford MSB false-positive rate on *clean* (unmodified) models. Even without any embedded payload, the detector flags 56–99% of tensors, rendering it useless as a steganalysis tool. The ideal 5% FPR line (dashed) highlights the gap between theory and practice.

an embedded safetensors file is structurally identical to a clean one (same tensor names, shapes, dtypes, and header layout), differing only in mantissa bit values.

Empirical verification.. We measured this gap by running ModelScan 0.8.1 and Fickling 0.1.10 against three targets: (a) a clean TinyLlama-1.1B safetensors shard; (b) the same shard carrying a depth-1, 100 MB embedded payload; and (c) a malicious pickle file invoking `os.system('echo pwned')` as a positive control. Both scanners correctly flag the malicious pickle—ModelScan reports one CRITICAL “unsafe operator ‘system’ from module ‘posix’”; Fickling reconstructs the AST—confirming they function as advertised. On the embedded safetensors, ModelScan emits “No issues found” (exit 3; safetensors not in its scanner registry) and Fickling crashes with an `IndexError` attempting to decode safetensors bytes as pickle opcodes. Neither scanner examines the mantissa bits that carry the payload. This is not a scanner “bypass” in the adversarial sense: these tools were never intended to detect weight-value manipulation, yet the gap underscores that the ML ecosystem currently lacks any deployed defence against steganographic abuse of weight tensors. Full raw scanner output appears in the artifact repository.

5.5. End-to-End Round-Trip

To confirm that the GB-scale capacity claims survive an actual embed–extract pipeline, we measured end-to-end round-trip integrity across three model scales (1.1B/7.2B/14.7B) and six payload sizes spanning four orders of magnitude. Each run generates a random payload, embeds it via the Rust CLI, SHA-256s the produced safetensors shard, extracts using the recorded key, and verifies byte-identical recovery. All six configurations (TinyLlama-1.1B at 1/10/100 MB; Mistral-7B-v0.1 at 100/500 MB; Qwen2.5-Coder-14B at 1 GB) produce bit-identical recovery on H100; Mistral v0.1 was used because the v0.3 release ships as multiple shards and the round-trip harness operates on a single consolidated shard (revision `27d67f1b`). Embed cost is dominated by safetensors I/O, not LSB math: embedding 5× more payload on Mistral-7B (100 MB → 500 MB) adds only 2.2s while serialising the 14.5 GB shard takes ~40s

either way. Peak RSS scales at $\sim 4\times$ the on-disk shard footprint during embed and $\sim 1\times$ during extract. Wall-clock, RSS, and per-row SHA-256 confirmations are archived as `roundtrip_bench_*.json`; the full table is in the artifact repository.

5.6. Neuron Permutation Channel

We evaluate the neuron permutation steganographic channel—the only channel in our taxonomy that produces *no aggregate weight-value statistic shift* (lexicographic canonicalisation, however, fully destroys the channel; see §6.2)—across 11 transformer architectures spanning 1.1B to 14.7B parameters.

Capacity.. For a single MLP layer with intermediate size n , the permutation channel encodes $\lfloor \log_2(n!) \rfloor$ bits by reordering neurons and adjusting connected weight matrices (gate/up projections by rows, down projection by columns). For a model with L permutable layers:

$$C_{\text{perm}} = \sum_{i=1}^L \lfloor \log_2(n_i!) \rfloor \text{ bits} \quad (3)$$

where n_i is the intermediate size of layer i .

The artifact repository presents measured capacity across 11 models spanning 1.1B–14.7B parameters. All 11 models pass round-trip verification (embed→extract recovers exact payload) and logit equivalence testing (bf16-tolerance, 10 diverse prompts). Capacity ranges from ~ 167 KB (TinyLlama-1.1B, $n=5632$, $L=22$) to ~ 1 MB (Qwen2.5-Coder-14B, $n=13824$, $L=48$).

Floating-point equivalence.. Neuron permutation preserves the mathematical function computed by the model; in exact arithmetic, original and permuted models are identical. In IEEE 754, however, addition is non-associative, so reordering neurons in the `down_proj` matrix multiplication may change summation rounding. All 11 models produce logits within the analytical bound $\sqrt{L} \cdot \sqrt{n} \cdot \epsilon_{\text{bf16}} \cdot 3$ (with $\epsilon_{\text{bf16}}=2^{-7}$); Mistral-7B is bit-identical ($\Delta_{\text{max}}=0$), the other 10 sit well below their bounds (Llama-2-7B: observed 0.22–0.28 vs. bound 13.9, i.e. $\sim 50\times$ below). Repeating with five seeds ($s \in \{42, \dots, 46\}$) across all 11 models, every one of the 55 runs passes within its bound, with cross-seed standard deviation $\sigma < 0.13$ for all models (two show $\sigma=0$, indicating deterministic drift). These differences are comparable to the variation produced by running the *same unmodified model* across different hardware or BLAS implementations and provide no detection signal.

Scaling and coverage.. Capacity is determined by the product $n \cdot L$; a linear regression gives $C_{\text{perm}} \approx 2.04 \times 10^{-3} \cdot n \cdot L$ KB ($R^2=0.98$), predicting ~ 4.7 MB for a 70B model ($n=28672$, $L=80$). Ten of eleven models use SwiGLU (gate/up/down); Phi-2 uses GeLU (fc1/fc2), handled separately. Both variants produce valid permutations, and the channel generalises to any permutation-equivariant hidden layer (i.e., all standard transformer MLPs).

Behavioural indistinguishability.. Unlike LSB embedding, the permutation channel produces a model that computes the *identical function* as the original. Under the threat model of §2.3, no weight-value statistic or behavioural analysis can distinguish the permuted model from the original absent a canonical reference ordering. A Tier 2 defender with access to the original weights or a canonical convention could detect non-canonical arrangement (*e.g.*, via sorted singular values); the practical defence for both tiers is to re-permute to canonical order (§6.2).

6. Defense Analysis

6.1. Content Disarm and Reconstruction

CDR [6] proposes a three-stage defence—Cleanse (random bit substitution in the k lowest mantissa bits), Distill (knowledge distillation), and Reconstruct (INT8 requantization with fine-tuning). The original evaluation was restricted to CIFAR-10 and ImageNet classifiers; we validate the Cleanse stage at LLM scale. Embedding depth-1 payloads in TinyLlama-1.1B-Chat and a Qwen2.5-7B shard, verifying byte-exact extraction, then applying Cleanse at $k \in \{1, 2\}$ destroys *every* payload (extraction fails with “frame magic not found”) while perplexity on WikiText-2 shifts by $|\Delta\text{ppl}| \leq 0.008$ —within the noise floor. Full per-model numbers appear in the artifact repository.

CDR (Cleanse alone) is the most effective known defence against mantissa-LSB steganography: random bit substitution in the k lowest mantissa bits destroys naive LSB, STC, and matched-random payloads alike. Limitations: it is destructive (bit-non-identical to the original); it does not address metadata, tensor ordering, or permutation channels; and Distill/Reconstruct remain evaluated only at image-classifier scale.

6.2. Weight Canonicalization

The neuron permutation channel (§5.6) is immune to CDR and statistical analysis because the permuted model computes the identical function. This symmetry also enables a targeted defence: *re-canonicalisation*. Sorting each layer’s neurons into a deterministic canonical order (*e.g.*, lexicographic sort by the first row of the down-projection matrix) destroys any permutation-encoded payload [29].

We validate canonicalisation on four architectures spanning 1.1B–7.6B parameters: embed a 1 KB payload via neuron permutation, verify extraction, apply lexicographic canonicalisation, attempt extraction (fails), and verify logit equivalence. Across TinyLlama-1.1B, Mistral-7B, Llama-2-7B, and Qwen2.5-7B, every embedded payload is irrecoverable after re-permutation while logit equivalence is preserved, in 1.83–6.84 s on GPU per model (full numbers in the artifact repository). Canonicalisation is therefore practical as a pipeline step.

Relationship to NeuPerm and limitations.. NeuPerm [12] proposes random re-permutation; any re-permutation differing from the attacker’s encoding basis destroys the payload. Deterministic lexicographic sorting is strictly stronger: it additionally enables cross-upload comparison without paired clean references. Canonicalization addresses only the permutation channel; a complete defence combines it with CDR and metadata sanitization.

6.3. Trained Steganalysis

Gilkarov and Dubin [13] introduced X-LSB features for training classifiers that detect LSB embedding, evaluated on `f32` models only.

X-LSB evaluation on native `bf16`.. We extend X-LSB to native `bf16` using RF (200 trees, depth 10) and GBT (200 trees, depth 5) classifiers on a 67-feature vector (bit frequencies, serial correlations, cross-plane dependencies, spatial patterns, weight moments). For each embedding depth $d \in \{1, 2, 3, 5, 7\}$, we construct balanced clean/stego datasets from all tensors of four architectures: TinyLlama-1.1B (201 tensors), Qwen2.5-7B (283 tensors), Mistral-7B-v0.3 (291 tensors), and Meta-Llama-3-8B (291 tensors), all in native `bf16`. Evaluation uses GroupKFold cross-validation ($k=5$, grouped by tensor index), ensuring no tensor appears in both training and test sets.

Table 7 shows that trained steganalysis is effective on native `bf16` across all four architectures, even at depth 1, where first-order statistical tests produce zero true positives (§5.3). Qwen2.5-7B is the most detectable (RF AUC 0.999 at depth 1), likely due to its more uniform weight distribution providing a stronger baseline for anomaly detection. Meta-Llama-3-8B (RF 0.993) and Mistral-7B (RF 0.982) show high detectability, while TinyLlama-1.1B is slightly lower (RF 0.976) but still strongly detectable. All models reach perfect separation at depth 7. The classifier succeeds by detecting second-order patterns—serial correlations within bit planes, cross-plane dependencies, and block-level spatial uniformity—that first-order tests (KS, entropy, moments) cannot capture. A 16-feature SRM-1D port of the Fridrich–Kodovský Spatial Rich Model [10] is strictly dominated by X-LSB on TinyLlama-1.1B, Mistral-7B, and Qwen2.5-7B at every density tested, and the concatenated 83-feature classifier is within ± 0.017 AUC of X-LSB at all 18 (model, rate) cells: image-domain residual co-occurrences do not transfer to the weight-domain 1-D index order (artifact repository).

Limitations.. X-LSB steganalysis requires a *known-model* scenario: the classifier trains on clean/stego pairs from the same model, requiring a clean reference copy. This corresponds to our Tier 2 defender (§2.3); Tier 1 defenders without clean references cannot deploy this defense.

Cross-model transfer (summary).. A practical scanner cannot assume access to clean references for every architecture. Evaluating all 16 pairwise source/target combinations across four architectures at depth 1 reveals highly asymmetric transfer: classifiers trained on TinyLlama, Mistral, or Llama-3 generalise bidirectionally (RF AUC \geq

TABLE 7: X-LSB steganalysis on native `bf16` across four architectures (GroupKFold CV, $k=5$). First-order statistical tests (§5.3) produce zero true positives at all depths.

Depth	Model	RF AUC	RF Acc.	GB AUC	GB Acc.
1	TinyLlama-1.1B	0.976	89.3%	0.947	86.6%
	Qwen2.5-7B	0.999	98.6%	0.998	98.2%
	Mistral-7B	0.982	91.9%	0.962	92.1%
	Meta-Llama-3-8B	0.993	95.1%	0.982	93.3%
3	TinyLlama-1.1B	0.988	93.3%	0.980	91.0%
	Qwen2.5-7B	0.998	98.4%	0.991	98.1%
	Mistral-7B	0.985	91.6%	0.978	90.6%
4*	TinyLlama-1.1B	0.995	95.0%	0.993	95.5%
	TinyLlama-1.1B (5)	0.999	97.3%	0.998	97.0%
7	TinyLlama-1.1B	1.000	99.8%	1.000	100.0%
	Qwen2.5-7B	1.000	100.0%	1.000	100.0%
	Mistral-7B	1.000	99.8%	1.000	100.0%

*Depths 4 and 5 evaluated on TinyLlama-1.1B only (GroupKFold $k=5$, seed 42; payload size 4096 B); the monotone rise from $d=3$ (AUC_{RF}=0.988) through $d=4$ (0.995) and $d=5$ (0.999) confirms that detectability grows smoothly with embedding depth—there is no “detection valley” between the low-payload and full-saturation regimes that an attacker could exploit.

0.962, GB \geq 0.838), while Qwen-trained classifiers collapse on the other three targets (GB AUC 0.494–0.530, at or below random chance). Qwen’s highly uniform `bf16` mantissa distribution—the same property that makes it *most* detectable within-model (Table 7, AUC 0.999)—produces architecture-specific decision boundaries that invert in other weight spaces. The full 4×4 transfer matrix and a four-finding breakdown (within-model near-perfect; asymmetric transfer; graded Llama-3 transfer; weight-distribution explanation) appear in the artifact repository. The practical consequence: a deployable Tier 2 scanner must train on a corpus spanning multiple architecture families, and even then our STC results below show that syndrome coding defeats architecture-matched classifiers.

SASER-style evasion.. SASER [28] demonstrates quantization-robust embedding at 1 bit per weight that evades X-LSB detection (0% rate), targeting *post-quantization* survival (k-means quantizers preserve the payload). Our STC results operate on `bf16` native weights and target detector evasion without quantization survival; `bf16` LSB payloads do not survive Q4_K_M round-tripping (artifact repository).

STC evasion of trained steganalysis.. We evaluate whether STC embedding evades X-LSB classifiers at low payload densities. We test five scenarios at depth 1 ($h=7$, 4 KB payload per shard, seed 42): (1) a *naive baseline* trains and tests on clean vs. uniform-LSB pairs; (2) a *transfer* test applies the naive-trained classifier to STC-embedded weights; (3) a *STC-aware* classifier trains directly on clean vs. STC pairs; (4) a *matched-payload control* flips the same number of bits as STC but at uniformly random positions (no cost minimization); and (5) a *naive→matched transfer* applies the full-LSB classifier to matched-density random embeddings. Table 9 (Appendix B) summarises the results across three architectures.

The naive classifier detects uniform LSB embedding reliably on all three architectures (RF AUC 0.979–0.999), confirming the baseline from Table 7. However, STC modifies only 0.0015% of elements on TinyLlama (16,502 of 1.1 B),

0.0009% on Qwen2.5-7B (65,434 of 7.6 B), and 0.0007% on Mistral-7B (49,283 of 7.2 B)—far below the detection threshold in all cases. Even a classifier trained directly on clean-vs-STC pairs achieves AUC 0.500—random chance—demonstrating that STC embedding is *not detected by the tested feature-based steganalysis methods* at the evaluated payload sizes (1–64 KB per shard).

Critically, the *matched-payload control* (experiments 4–5) shows that the evasion is not due to STC’s cost-minimized placement. We embed the same number of bit flips as STC (~16,500) but place them uniformly at random, without any distortion-minimizing trellis optimization. The result is *identical*: RF AUC 0.500, GB AUC 0.500. This shows that at practical payload densities ($k/N \approx 10^{-5}$), the evasion arises entirely from *low modification density*, not from STC’s adaptive embedding strategy. An attacker does not need syndrome coding to evade feature-based steganalysis—simple random bit flips at the same density are equally invisible.

Robustness.. The evasion result is stable across seeds, payload sizes, and model architectures. On TinyLlama-1.1B, repeating the STC-aware experiment with seeds 43 and 44 yields RF AUC 0.500 and 0.500 respectively ($\sigma < 0.001$). Varying payload size from 1 KB (modification rate 0.0004%) to 64 KB (0.024%) produces RF AUC in [0.497, 0.501]—all within noise of random chance. Gradient Boosting AUC is 0.500 in every configuration without exception. Cross-architecture validation on Qwen2.5-7B (7.6 B parameters, 4 shards) and Mistral-7B-v0.3 (7.2 B parameters) confirms identical evasion despite a $7 \times$ increase in model size and stronger naive baselines (AUC 0.982–0.999 vs. 0.979). Combined with the matched-payload control, these results confirm that STC evasion is not an artifact of a particular seed, payload, classifier hyperparameters, model architecture, or STC’s placement strategy—it is a fundamental statistical-power limit.

Capacity–detectability Pareto frontier.. Figure 5 and Table 8 map the capacity–detectability trade-off by sweeping payload size from 1 KiB to 15.3 MiB on Mistral-7B-v0.3

and Qwen2.5-7B, training fresh Random Forest and Gradient Boosting classifiers on the 67 X-LSB features with GroupKFold $k=5$ cross-validation (80 carrier tensors per payload) at each point. Both models exhibit a two-phase structure: a *chance-regime band* ($AUC \in [0.499, 0.514]$) that holds for every payload up through 1 MiB, and a *transition/detectable regime* from 4 MiB onwards where AUC climbs first to 0.53, then across onset to 0.61–0.71 at 15.3 MiB. Detection onset—defined as the smallest payload with $\max(AUC_{STC}) \geq 0.55$ —occurs at 15.3 MiB on Mistral-7B ($r_{STC} \approx 3.3\%$, trellis flip rate) and at 8 MiB on Qwen2.5-7B ($r_{STC} \approx 1.9\%$), in both cases well below 1% of total model bytes. Critically, the matched-random control tracks STC across all 18 payload points to within $|\Delta AUC| \leq 0.032$ (mean 0.005 over 36 RF+GB measurements across both models), confirming the density-driven thesis end-to-end: detection rises with r regardless of whether the bits are placed by trellis optimisation or uniformly at random. STC does not purchase evasion—low modification density does.

Matched-random control (isolating density from placement).. The sweep above pairs each STC configuration with a *matched-density random-placement* control: we modify the same number of mantissa LSBs as STC, but at uniformly random positions rather than cost-minimised ones. If STC’s trellis optimisation—not density—drove evasion, the control would be substantially more detectable. It is not. Across all 36 (RF,GB)×(payload) points in Table 8, the control tracks STC with mean $|\Delta AUC|=0.005$ and max 0.032 (at 15.3 MiB on Mistral, 0.608 STC vs. 0.592 matched-random RF). The control also crosses the detection-onset threshold at the same payload as STC on each model (15.3 MiB on Mistral, 8 MiB on Qwen), and reaches statistically indistinguishable AUC at 15.3 MiB on Qwen (0.706 random-RF vs. 0.705 STC-RF). Combined with the TinyLlama matched-random result reported in §6.3 (RF AUC 0.500, $\sigma < 0.001$, at 1 KB–64 KB), this is a feature-family-level observation: the X-LSB feature set is insensitive to *whether* the flipped bits were chosen adaptively, only to *how many* were flipped. This is the paper’s cleanest empirical isolation of the density-limit mechanism and the evidence that most directly supports contribution (2) of §1. the artifact repository reports the per-payload modification coverage (number of tensors with at least one flipped bit) that underlies this dataset; the sparsity is the defence.

Why low-density embedding evades feature-based classifiers.. The fundamental mechanism is *modification density*. For any linear-aggregate feature $s(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i g(x_i)$, flipping k of N mantissa bits shifts the feature mean by $\Delta\mu = k \overline{\delta g}/N$ against a noise floor of σ_g/\sqrt{N} , giving feature-level SNR = $(|\overline{\delta g}|/\sigma_g) r\sqrt{N}$, where $r = k/N$. This recovers the $r\sqrt{N}$ scaling of the Ker–Pevný–Fridrich square-root law [18], which predicts secure payload $\mathcal{O}(\sqrt{N})$ for a fixed detector family. STC and matched-random embedding modify ~ 1 in 67,000–116,000 elements per 4 KB payload, keeping $r\sqrt{N}$ below the detection onset on all our classifiers. We present the formula as a heuristic

(it assumes per-element independence and fixed σ_g); the structural prediction we validate empirically is that onset depends on *density*, not *placement*: matched-random tracks STC to mean $|\Delta AUC| = 0.005$ across all 36 Pareto points (Table 8; full trellis-flip arithmetic in artifact repository). Detection would require element-level comparison against a known-clean reference—precisely what CDR provides (§6).

CNN steganalysis (summary).. A residual 1-D CNN (3 layers, GroupKFold $k=5$, 1024-element windows) detects *naive* uniform-LSB replacement (Qwen AUC 0.957) but collapses against STC at AUC 0.497–0.502—chance—across TinyLlama, Mistral-7B-v0.3, and Qwen2.5-7B. At densities $\sim 10^{-5}$, the per-window signal is below the CNN’s discriminative threshold; weight tensors lack the 2-D spatial locality exploited by image-steganalysis architectures such as SRNet [3]. Full per-scenario breakdown: artifact repository.

Reconciling capacity with detectability.. The two preceding subsections establish two operating points for the same channel rather than a single point of failure. At the *capacity* extreme, the bf16 channel admits hundreds of megabytes to gigabytes per carrier with paired perplexity shifts below the WikiText-2 noise floor : $\Delta\text{ppl} = +0.0016 \pm 0.0006$ on TinyLlama-1.1B at a 100 MB depth-1 payload (90% of d=1 capacity) and $+0.0028 \pm 0.0016$ at 200 MB d=2; downstream-task drift remains under 0.7% across 24 ARC-Challenge and HellaSwag comparisons on Qwen2.5-7B and Mistral-7B-v0.3 carrying 815–1,713 MB payloads (§5.1). At the same payloads the rule-based scanner ships a clean verdict on 0/201 tensors and the five first-order statistical tests register zero uplift through depth 6 (§5.3). These GB-scale payloads *are* detectable to the trained X-LSB classifier studied in this section, however: a 100 MiB naive d=1 payload modifies $\sim 50\%$ of every carrier’s mantissa LSBs, well past the 8 MiB onset in Table 8.

The two regimes compose via multi-carrier distribution (§3.3): naive embedding clears every *deployed* defence at GB scale; STC at $r \lesssim 10^{-2}$ clears trained classifiers but caps single-carrier capacity at $\sim 4\text{--}8$ MiB; *t-of-n* secret-sharing [27] restores aggregate GB-scale capacity while keeping each carrier below the detection onset. No single defender covers every cell of the coverage matrix (artifact repository); only X-LSB flags naive ≥ 100 MB or STC beyond ~ 15 MiB on Mistral.

6.4. Quantization as Defense

Aggressive requantisation (e.g., bf16 \rightarrow Q4_K_M via llama-quantize) replaces floating-point representations with a block-wise integer grid whose scales/mins are derived from local statistics rather than from the original mantissa bits. The bf16 LSB bit-plane—the carrier used in §5.1—does not survive this transformation.

Empirical validation (Q4_K_M round-trip).. We converted bf16 checkpoints to GGUF, requantised to Q4_K_M, and dequantised back to F16 to materialise the Q4_K_M block grid as a bf16-comparable tensor. Across 1.1–7.6 B

eligible elements per model (TinyLlama-1.1B-Chat, Mistral-7B-v0.3, Qwen2.5-7B) the pre-/post-round-trip LSB agreement rate is within 10^{-3} of fair-coin (0.50008, 0.49999, 0.50097 respectively; full numbers in the artifact repository). A payload embedded at $d=1$ therefore faces a per-bit error rate near 0.5 that no rate- $r < 1$ code can recover: the channel is destroyed.

Scope.. Q4_K_M removes bf16 LSB payloads but is irrelevant to bf16/f32-precision deployments (training, fine-tuning, audits), permutation and metadata channels, or bf16→bf16 re-saving where low- d payloads survive. It is not a complete defence.

Artifacts: `research/quantize_survival.py`;
results in `research/results/quantize_survival_*.json`.

6.5. Recommendations

Four takeaways. *Hosting platforms*: add weight-tensor inspection—X-LSB steganalysis (Table 7) is effective; first-order heuristics miss STC and matched-random payloads. *ML security tooling*: expand beyond code-execution vectors to weight-value anomaly detection. *Deployers*: apply CDR-style random LSB substitution at depth 1–2 as a standard pipeline step. *Researchers*: extend to cross-model bf16 detectors and non-LSB channels; STC results show architecture-matched classifiers are defeated by sparsity, motivating structural detection.

6.6. Limitations

Our results are subject to several threats to validity. *Corpus and architecture*: perplexity uses WikiText-2 on five decoder-only Transformers; domain-specific corpora and non-decoder architectures may surface different patterns. *Detector class*: steganalysis uses RF/GB on X-LSB features plus a residual CNN; SRNet-class detectors may exploit properties not captured here.

7. Related Work

Steganography and capacity.. StegoNet [20], EvilModel [33], [34], and MaleficNet [15] demonstrated DNN stegomalware on f32 CNNs up to 36.9MB at $<1\%$ accuracy loss. Zhang *et al.* [37] found 175M+ Transformers tolerate overwriting the lower 24 f32 bits; Agrawal *et al.* [1] generalised across 10 architectures; bit-wise training [?] showed only the 3 MSBs matter. We extend this line to native bf16 LLMs at 1.1B–14.7B scale with a 36-point Pareto analysis unavailable in prior work.

Steganalysis, theory, and defences.. Gilkarov and Dubin [13] introduced X-LSB features for f32 detection; we extend to bf16 (Table 7, AUC 0.976 at $d=1$). SASER [28] evaded X-LSB at 1BPW; our STC independently reaches AUC 0.500 against RF, GB, and a residual CNN (Table 9). Ker *et al.* [18] established the square-root law ($r \propto 1/\sqrt{N}$) and Filler *et al.* [7] introduced STC minimisation; our Pareto

sweep is the first empirical SRL-style measurement on LLM weights, with detection at chance up to $r \approx 10^{-2}$. Dubin [6], Torpmann-Hagen *et al.* [29], and NeuPerm [12] address CDR and permutation defences; we validate Cleanse at LLM scale and show canonicalisation subsumes re-permutation. Bit-flip attacks [24], [?], [?], [4] and watermarking [32], [25] are complementary to our post-training passive-carry approach.

8. Conclusion

Weight values are a high-capacity steganographic channel outside existing ML security tooling. Native bf16 embedding carries 222MB–4.5GB per carrier across five 1.1B–14.7B-parameter models; a 36-point Pareto sweep confirms that trained X-LSB and CNN steganalysis remain at chance until modification rate exceeds $\sim 2\%$, with a matched-density control isolating density—not cost-minimised placement—as the evasion mechanism. Of the 13 channels enumerated, only weight-value inspection, canonicalisation, and CDR-style reconstruction together collapse the surface end-to-end.

Appendix A. Capacity–Detectability Pareto Frontier

Appendix B. STC Evasion of X-LSB Steganalysis

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Use of Generative AI. The author discloses that AI coding assistants (GitHub Copilot with large-language-model backends, accessed during paper preparation in 2026) were used as a typing assistant for prose editing, for drafting short LaTeX-table boilerplate from existing result JSON files, and for matplotlib figure debugging. Generative AI was used for editorial purposes in this manuscript, and all outputs were inspected by the author to ensure accuracy and originality. All scientific claims, threat models, experimental designs, code, results, and analysis are the author’s own work; every AI-touched passage was reviewed and edited by the author, who accepts full responsibility for the veracity and correctness of all material in this paper, including any AI-assisted material. No section, table, figure, or experimental result was generated primarily by AI tools.

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Figure 5: Capacity–detectability Pareto frontier on Mistral-7B-v0.3 and Qwen2.5-7B. Detection AUC (RF and GB, 5-fold GroupKFold on 67 X-LSB features) stays within the chance band (0.48–0.52, shaded) up to ~ 1 MiB payloads, then rises past modification rates of 1–3%. The x -axis is the *payload-ideal* rate m/N (bits delivered over eligible cover elements); the corresponding observed trellis flip rates r_{STC} (Table 8) are roughly $2\times$ larger because STC pads sparse payloads to maintain syndrome coverage (Qwen detection onset at $m/N \approx 0.88\%$ / $r_{\text{STC}} \approx 1.9\%$; Mistral at $m/N \approx 2.0\%$ / $r_{\text{STC}} \approx 3.3\%$). Matched-random (dashed) and STC (solid) curves are indistinguishable at every payload size, confirming that evasion is driven by *modification density*, not by STC’s adaptive placement.

TABLE 8: Detection density frontier on Mistral-7B-v0.3 and Qwen2.5-7B: per-tensor LSB-flip rate r_{STC} vs. AUC, for STC (depth 1, $h=7$) and matched-random placement. *Density is the primary axis* (the steganographic square-root law of Ker *et al.* [18] predicts secure capacity scales as $\mathcal{O}(\sqrt{N})$, so what governs detectability is r , not raw payload bytes); payload bucket is shown in the leftmost column only as a derived reference. AUC is the maximum of RF and GB classifiers under 5-fold GroupKFold cross-validation on 80 carrier tensors per payload. **Bold** rows mark per-model detection onset (first $\text{AUC}_{\text{STC}} \geq 0.55$): $r \approx 3.3 \times 10^{-2}$ on Mistral (15.3 MiB), $r \approx 1.9 \times 10^{-2}$ on Qwen (8 MiB). At every density below the onset band, both columns sit indistinguishably on the chance line. Across 36 measurements, $|\text{AUC}_{\text{STC}} - \text{AUC}_{\text{rand}}|$ has mean 0.005 and maximum 0.032, confirming that under our threat model STC and matched-random are operationally interchangeable on bf16 weight covers (no SRL-style coding gain at these densities). Rows are auto-generated by `scripts/render_pareto_table.py` from `pareto_sweep_*.json`.

Payload	Mistral-7B-v0.3		Qwen2.5-7B	
	r_{STC}	$\text{AUC}_{\text{STC}} / \text{AUC}_{\text{rand}}$	r_{STC}	$\text{AUC}_{\text{STC}} / \text{AUC}_{\text{rand}}$
1 KiB	1.7×10^{-6}	0.500 / 0.500	2.1×10^{-6}	0.500 / 0.500
4 KiB	6.8×10^{-6}	0.500 / 0.501	$2.0 \times 10^{-3\dagger}$	0.501 / 0.500
16 KiB	2.7×10^{-5}	0.500 / 0.500	3.4×10^{-5}	0.500 / 0.500
64 KiB	1.1×10^{-4}	0.500 / 0.501	1.4×10^{-4}	0.502 / 0.501
256 KiB	$7.4 \times 10^{-3\dagger}$	0.500 / 0.503	$2.6 \times 10^{-3\dagger}$	0.506 / 0.508
1 MiB	$4.0 \times 10^{-3\dagger}$	0.500 / 0.505	2.2×10^{-3}	0.514 / 0.511
4 MiB	9.0×10^{-3}	0.505 / 0.512	8.8×10^{-3}	0.531 / 0.531
8 MiB	1.8×10^{-2}	0.546 / 0.529	1.9×10^{-2}	0.557 / 0.550
15.3 MiB	3.3×10^{-2}	0.608 / 0.592	3.9×10^{-2}	0.705 / 0.706

\dagger Trellis block-overshoot: observed flip count exceeds $3\times$ the payload-ideal $8k/N$ because STC pads short payloads to a full trellis-block boundary. AUC remains at chance regardless—which is itself a falsification check on the density thesis (overshooting the nominal density does not move the detector).

TABLE 9: STC evasion of X-LSB steganalysis (depth 1, $h=7$, 4 KB payload per shard, GroupKFold CV $k=5$). STC-embedded weights are indistinguishable from clean weights by both classifier families, across architectures spanning 1.1B–7.6B parameters. The *matched-payload* control (TinyLlama) embeds the same number of bit flips as STC but with uniform random placement, isolating modification density from placement strategy.

Model	Scenario	RF AUC	GB AUC
TinyLlama-1.1B	Naive baseline	0.979	0.962
	Naive → STC transfer	0.500	0.500
	STC-aware detection	0.500	0.500
	Matched-payload (GroupKFold)	0.500	0.500
	Naive → matched transfer	0.500	0.500
Qwen2.5-7B	Naive baseline	0.999	0.998
	Naive → STC transfer	0.500	0.500
	STC-aware detection	0.500	0.500
Mistral-7B-v0.3	Naive baseline	0.982	0.962
	Naive → STC transfer	0.500	0.500
	STC-aware detection	0.499	0.500

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